

NASA EVS-3 PROPOSAL: SUBMESOSCALE OCEAN DYNAMICS AND VERTICAL TRANSPORT

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1.0 Executive Summary

A major difficulty in simulating Earth’s climate system is that there are interactions across scales, so that the large time and space scales can be sensitive to processes on small scales. As the computational resolution of global ocean models has improved, scientists have begun to suspect that kilometer-scale eddies and fronts, called “*submesoscale*” variability, have a net effect on ocean-atmosphere heat exchange that is larger than the heating from the greenhouse effect (Su et al. 2018). State-of-the-art computer models agree in predicting that these eddies have important long-term effects on the upper-ocean, but their predictions are sensitive to relatively small details in model physics and implementation. The resolution and detail of these simulations has surpassed our ability to ‘ground truth’ them with spaceborne or in situ sensors. There is thus a pressing need for a comprehensive benchmark data set on these submesoscale motions to address this important source of uncertainty in simulating the global ocean.

This is a proposal to test the hypothesis that submesoscale ocean dynamics make important contributions to vertical exchange of climate and biological variables in the upper ocean. This will require coordinated application of newly-developed in situ and remote sensing techniques, and it will provide an unprecedented view of the physics of submesoscale eddies and fronts and their effects on vertical transport in the upper ocean. The **Sub-Mesoscale Ocean Dynamics Experiment (S-MODE)** will use measurements from a novel combination of platforms and instruments (Fig. 1.1. and Table 1.1.), along with data analysis and modeling, to test the hypothesis.

Threshold Science Objectives	Quantitatively measure the three-dimensional structure of the submesoscale features responsible for vertical exchange in the upper ocean
	Understand the relation between the velocity (and other surface properties) measured by remote sensing at the surface and that within and just below the surface boundary layer
Baseline Science Objectives	Quantify the role of air-sea interaction and surface forcing in the dynamics and vertical velocity of submesoscale variability
	Examine vertical transport processes at submesoscales to mesoscales

Figure 1.1: A sketch of the S-MODE investigation, depicting the experimental site offshore of California and the platforms and aircraft instruments that will be employed. The experimental plan involves a two-week pilot campaign and two, 25-day intensive operating periods during spring and fall of 2021, with 10-15 flights in each period. The nominal site is 300 km from San Francisco.

In a region extending 300km offshore of San Francisco (Fig. 3.2), we will collect simultaneous measurements using several airborne instruments (Table 1.1), including the NASA DopplerScatt instrument, the NASA PRISM instrument, the SIO MASS instrument and the UCLA MOSES instrument. In conjunction with the measurements from aircraft (nominally a NASA King Air B200, NASA ER-2, and a commercial Twin Otter DHC-6), in situ data will be obtained using surface drifters, wave-propelled autonomous vehicles, Lagrangian floats that follow the 3D flow, vertically profiling autonomous underwater vehicles, and a research vessel (Table 1.1).

Total estimated cost to NASA: \$30M

Total investigation cost estimate: \$30M

Schedule summary:

1. July 1, 2019: start of project
2. April 2020: Pilot year, 2-week pilot campaign (backup, Sept 2020)
3. April 2021: 1-month campaign (backup September 2021)
4. September 2021: 1-month campaign (backup April 2022)
5. 2021/2022: Data cal/val and delivery (delivery to data center 3-6 months after campaign)
6. 2022-2024: Science analysis, publications
7. June 30, 2024: end of project

Instrument	Variables	Platform
NASA-JPL DopplerScatt	Ocean surface current and wind	NASA KingAir B200
UCLA MOSES	Sea surface temperature	NASA KingAir B200
NASA-JPL PRISM	Ocean color (hyperspectral imagery)	NASA ER-2
SIO MASS (topographic lidar, infrared, visible & hyperspectral imagery)	Directional Wave spectra; Sea surface topography; Sea surface temperature; ocean color (hyperspectral imagery)	Twin Otter DHC-6 (Twin Otter International)
Ocean surface drifters with GPS	Upper-ocean current	Deployed from ship (qty 100)
Meteorological package; current profiler; fixed-depth CTDs; bio-optics	Surface fluxes and wind; Upper-ocean temperature and salinity; velocity profiles, chl and beam attenuation	Wave Gliders (qty 4)
CTD, current profiler, bio-optics, turbulence	Upper-ocean temperature, salinity, velocity, chl and backscatter, float tracking	Seagliders (qty 5)
Lagrangian floats (with CTD, bio-optics, ADCPs)	Lagrangian trajectories, vertical velocity, temperature, salinity, turbulence	Univ. Washington Lagrangian Floats
Current Profilers, Underway CTD	Upper-ocean temperature, salinity, velocity, chlorophyll,	Oceanographic research vessel

Table 1.1: Table of instruments, with color coding designating aircraft measurements (green), autonomous in situ platforms/vehicles (blue), and ship measurements (red).

This investigation will directly address a number of the science priorities, goals, and objectives of NASA’s Earth Science Research Program. Specifically, it will:

1. *Contribute to enhanced Earth system models*—it will provide the measurements needed to test the fidelity of rapidly evolving capabilities for numerical simulation of ocean physics and air-sea interaction across a range of scales, and it will dramatically advance understanding of the relationship between surface divergence, vertical transports, and primary productivity;
2. *Contribute to planning for future satellite observations*-- the *2017 Decadal Survey for Earth Science and Applications from Space* recommended consideration of a Doppler scatterometer Earth System Explorer mission (likely to be based on DopplerScatt); the proposed activities will also complement and help inform SWOT cal/val activities;
3. *Complement current projects in the NASA Earth Science Research Program*-- the project addresses questions that are central to interests and activities of many NASA projects, including the SWOT Science Team, the Ocean Vector Wind Science Team, the Ocean Surface Topography Science Team, the Physical Oceanography Program, the Ocean Biology and Biogeochemistry Program, and the NASA PACE and EXPORTS field programs.

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3.0 Science Investigation

The ocean surface boundary layer that lies at the interface of the ocean and the atmosphere makes up only a small fraction (about 2%) of the global oceans, but it plays a critical role in the climate system because it mediates the atmosphere-ocean exchange of important properties like heat, nutrients, oxygen, and carbon. Submesoscale ocean dynamics (horizontal wavelengths of 0.2-25 km, time scales of hours to days) are hypothesized to play an important role in vertical exchange, both between the atmosphere and the surface layer and between the surface layer and the deeper ocean. Our ability to simulate submesoscale ocean dynamics has outpaced our ability to observe them, and recent studies using high-resolution global ocean models suggest that vertical transport of heat by submesoscale variability is indeed a significant factor in the climate system; for example, Su et al. (2018) showed that improved resolution of submesoscale variability leads to changes in mean air-sea heat fluxes in the midlatitudes that are an order of magnitude larger than the global radiation imbalance associated with the greenhouse effect. **The goal of this proposal is to use measurements from the NASA airborne Doppler scatterometer (DopplerScatt), in combination with other aircraft and in situ data, to directly test the hypothesis that submesoscale ocean dynamics are important to vertical exchange in the upper ocean.**

Submesoscale currents and vertical transport

Oceanographers use the term ‘mesoscale’ to refer to oceanic variability on scales of 25-1000 km (i.e., eddies and ‘Rossby’ waves), which are smaller than the basin-scale gyres but larger than ‘small’ or ‘finescale’ variability on scales of O(1-100) m (e.g., surface gravity waves and classical 3D turbulent eddies). As a result of landmark research programs in the 1970s (MODE group, 1978) and the development of modern satellite altimetry in the 1990s (Chelton et al., 2001), mesoscale motions are well understood and routinely measured and tracked by operational models. More recently, however, as the resolution of models increased, it was discovered that there is an important class of motions at scales in between the ‘mesoscale’ and the ‘small’ scale. These motions became known as ‘submesoscale’ variability (McWilliams, 2016). The submesoscale range of scales overlaps substantially with familiar inertial currents and internal gravity waves, but the latter have very different kinematic and dynamical characteristics. In particular, as the resolution of models increases toward kilometer scales, an explosion of small scale variability occurs (Fig. 3.1) revealing the new submesoscale regime that is the focus of the proposed work.

Figure 3.1 Surface temperature for California Current model with a) mesoscale (12 km) resolution and b) submesoscale (0.75 km) resolution (from Capet et al. 2008). The rich set of predicted submesoscale fronts and eddies are the focus of the proposed campaign.

Submesoscale currents with horizontal wavelengths of 0.2-25 km provide a critical link between the highly anisotropic (nearly 2D), geostrophic mesoscale circulation and the fully 3D turbulent circulation of the weakly stratified upper ocean. Submesoscale variability is of great interest to oceanographers because it is hypothesized to play an important role in vertical exchange between the surface layer and the deeper interior ocean (Klein & Lapeyre 2009, Mahadevan 2014), to provide an energy sink for mesoscale eddies and a source for finescale motions (McWilliams 2016), and to control horizontal transport in the upper ocean through surface convergences and dispersion causing

material patchiness on scales between mesoscale and finescale (Lapeyre and Klein 2006, Levy and Martin 2013; D’Asaro et al. 2018). Submesoscale dynamics are pronounced at density fronts and filaments that give rise to frontogenesis and a range of submesoscale instabilities (Mahadevan and Tandon, 2006, Thomas et al., 2008).

The vertical transport of matter and energy in the ocean cannot be accomplished efficiently by the mesoscale and larger-scale flow fields, which have very small vertical velocities (of order 1-10 m/day or less). The transition from the mesoscale dynamical regime to the submesoscale regime is characterized by increasingly strong vertical velocities (Haine and Marshall, 1998). The distinctively large vertical velocities occur primarily in ageostrophic secondary circulations across the horizontal surface density gradients, and induce large vertical buoyancy flux (known as restratification) (Boccaletti et al., 2007) and large biogeochemical fluxes between the euphotic surface layer and underlying gradient layers (e.g., the nutricline; Levy et al., 2012; Omand et al., 2015). The associated vertical transport is hypothesized to have important consequences for oceanic biology, chemistry, and physics.

Our understanding of submesoscale motions and their vertical exchange comes primarily from numerical simulations. Although models with sufficient resolution¹ all predict the existence of submesoscale motions, there are large variations in their quantitative predictions. For example, Fig. 3.2 compares fields of surface relative vorticity (a variable that highlights submesoscales) for two models currently used to simulate the performance of the upcoming SWOT satellite (Wang et al., 2018; Chelton et al., 2018). Although they both show submesoscale fronts and eddies, the higher-resolution ROMS simulation shows a stronger dominance of cyclonic eddies over fronts, while the MITgcm shows a larger seasonal difference between March and September.

These differences highlight the uncertainties in such simulations. The key distinctive features of the submesoscale-- the sharp fronts, high vorticity at these fronts and associated large vertical velocities-- occur at the smallest scales resolved by the models. Their amplitudes are thus sensitive to resolution (e.g. Fig. 3.2) and thus to the details of the numerics and damping at the grid scale. Increasing the resolution toward 100m increases the strength of the submesoscale features, but also brings the grid to the same scales as the parameterized boundary layer turbulence. Proper subgrid schemes to deal with this overlap are still experimental. Furthermore, models and theory indicate both that submesoscale motions are sensitive to the boundary layer turbulence (e.g. turbulent thermal wind; McWilliams, 2016) and that the boundary layer turbulence itself is affected by the submesoscale gradients (D’Asaro et al., 2011). These effects are only partially included in models.

The physics of air-sea interaction at submesoscales is another poorly constrained factor in simulation of submesoscale dynamics and their associated vertical transport. Submesoscale vorticity can be much larger than the vertical component of Earth’s rotation rate, which can fundamentally alter the wind-driven vertical transports (known as Ekman pumping; Stern, 1965; McGillicuddy et al., 2007; 2008; Fig. 3.3). In addition, the boundary layer turbulence is primarily forced by air-sea fluxes that are computed from bulk-exchange coefficients that have not been validated at submesoscales. The fluxes can be modulated by the SST gradients at fronts (Friehe et al., 1991), by the frontal currents themselves and by variations in the surface wave field propagating across

¹ In this proposal, when we say “resolution” in reference to numerical simulations, we mean the grid size. When we say resolution in reference to measurements we mean the effective sample spacing, or the spacing over which the measurements are statistically independent. The spectral or wavelength resolution will be approximately twice the stated resolution value.

Figure 3.2 Surface vorticity off Central California in two submesoscale-resolving models in March (left column) and September (right column). Regional ROMS (top row 500 m resolution) and JPL-MITgcm (bottom row, ~ 2km resolution) show different structures and different seasonal evolution. The rectangle in the upper left shows our experiment domain. In all panels, the vorticity has been normalized by the local value of the Coriolis parameter.

The inset in the upper right panel is the normalized vorticity measured by DopplerScatt in the Gulf of Mexico (Fig. 3.6), shown with the same distance scaling and color scale as in the model fields-- we now have an exciting new capability for mapping ocean vorticity and divergence.

the velocity gradients of these fronts (Sullivan and McWilliams, 2010). Given these uncertainties, a major goal of the proposed work is to make detailed measurements of the submesoscale variability and compare these with model predictions.

Figure. 3.3 Left panel: The vertical velocity a depth of at 20 m depth for a region off the coast of central California based on a ROMS simulation of the California Current System with a 500-m grid. Right panel: the vorticity gradient contribution to wind-driven vertical velocity estimated from existing theory for the effect of ocean vorticity on wind-driven upwelling (Stern, 1965).

The complexity (Figs. 3.1-3.4), size and rapid evolution (hours to days) of submesoscale motions has made them difficult to measure.

They are much larger than ships, but small and rapidly evolving compared to typical ship surveys, small for many satellite remote sensing footprints, and difficult to distinguish from inertia-gravity waves because they occur on similar spatial and temporal scales. Over the last decade, new instrumentation and techniques have been developed to overcome these difficulties. Recent experiments have shown the benefit of using an observing system that combines multiple, diverse platforms that enables measurements across a range of spatial and temporal scales (Fig. 3.5,

Figure 3.4 VIIRS false color image of proposed study region offshore of San Francisco shows complex pattern in February 2016 due to mesoscale and submesoscale currents acting on a large phytoplankton bloom. The proposed campaign will use a combination of detailed quantitative mapping of velocity, chlorophyll, temperature, and other properties from aircraft with targeted in-situ measurements to overcome the observational challenges involved in sampling such a complex field in 3D (NASA image by Norman Kuring, NASA's Ocean Color Web.)

Shcherbina et al. 2013; D'Asaro et al. 2018). First, satellite remote sensing informs direct

aircraft remote sensing which, in turn, informs in-situ measurements. Second, multiple in-situ platforms, both ships and a variety of autonomous platforms, are combined to simultaneously measure large values of the km-scale density gradients, vorticity and divergence, that distinguish submesoscale motions from mesoscale and internal wave motions. Third, measurements are made in a Lagrangian coordinate system, tracking the evolving submesoscale features as they move within the larger, more energetic mesoscale currents. Finally, a new generation of Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) and neutrally buoyant float technology, can now measure vertical velocities and trajectories at submesoscale fronts (Fig. 3.5), thereby allowing direct evaluation of

vertical exchange due to submesoscale dynamics.

Figure 3.5 New observational methods are effective in measuring submesoscale vertical exchange (D'Asaro et al. 2018). Here, aircraft SST maps were used to locate a submesoscale eddy. Surface drifters were deployed into the eddy. Their patterns (a- black dots) were used to guide a ship survey (a- plan view white circles), which showed density front (b). A water-following Lagrangian float (red lines) was deployed near the front. The float moved into the front and measured the sinking of dense

water (b,c) at the front both from its motion and from an ADCP mounted on the float.

Why now?

Vertical velocities have proven exceedingly difficult to measure because they are so weak (~ 1 mm/s). There have been several technological advances in recent years that now allow us to make significant scientific advances:

1. NASA's DopplerScatt (Rodriguez et al. 2018) measures submesoscale velocities & winds at the surface that are directly linked to vertical motion and vertical fluxes, at a spatial resolution and synopticity that has never before been possible for ocean velocity measurements. **For the first time, we have the capability to make synoptic maps of the divergence and vorticity of ocean surface currents (Figs. 3.2 and 3.6), which are central to submesoscale dynamics and their role in vertical transport.**

2. Numerical ocean models can now simultaneously resolve a range of horizontal scales spanning $\sim 10^3$ - 10^5 m. They have been able to make clear predictions about the magnitude and physics of submesoscale variability for more than a decade, but our ability to test these predictions observationally has lagged behind.
3. Several new techniques have matured over the last couple of decades that allow direct in situ measurements of vertical velocity (Lagrangian floats and high-rate Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers, or ADCPs, equipped with an additional vertical beam and inertial motion package). Networks of autonomous platforms can also allow improved resolution and coverage of the velocity field and allow estimation of the vertical profile of horizontal divergence (closely linked to vertical motion).
4. New hyperspectral imaging sensors, such as the NASA-JPL Portable Remote Imaging SpectroMeter (PRISM) and SIO MASS, enable coincident measurements of physical and biological properties at the ocean surface that will allow investigation of how submesoscale circulations impact ecological dynamics and biogeochemical cycling.

Figure 3.6 Vorticity (left) and divergence (right) of surface currents measured by the aircraft-mounted DopplerScatt instrument in the Gulf of Mexico in April 2017 (Rodriguez et al. 2018). The ‘plume’ of positive vorticity in the left panel is associated with the Mississippi River outflow. The DopplerScatt swath width is about 25 km and the center of each swath is blanked out here. The associated surface currents are presented and discussed in Rodriguez et al. (2018). Vorticity and divergence have been normalized by the local value of the Coriolis parameter ($f=0.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$).

The need for sustained measurements

There are three principal reasons that addressing the hypothesis requires sustained measurements:

- (1) Temporal variability must be resolved in order to identify and separate the dynamical processes of interest. Submesoscale variability exists at scales overlapping with other classes of oceanic motions (higher frequency internal gravity wave variability and inertial currents), and data from single overflights will contain contributions from a mix of dynamical processes. Sustained measurements of different dynamical factors (like velocity and sea surface height/pressure) will allow these processes to be disentangled.
- (2) Any particular submesoscale feature (eddy or filament) evolves over a timescale of several days, and all the available in-situ observational tools for quantifying this evolution can only measure one submesoscale feature at a time. Thus, the need to have supporting in situ measurements from several submesoscale features per campaign drives a need to make measurements over several weeks.
- (3) Submesoscale dynamics are expected to depend sensitively on seasonally varying factors, like surface mixed-layer depth, winds, and surface heat fluxes. Theory and state-of-the-art numerical simulations produce different predictions for the seasonal cycle of submesoscale variability (e.g., Fig. 3.2), and it is thus imperative to have measurements from different

seasons (preferably fall, when mixed-layer depths are shallowest, and spring, when mixed-layer depths are deepest).

Relevance to NASA's science goals:

This project will directly address a number of the science priorities, goals, and objectives of NASA's Earth Science Research Program. Specifically, it will:

1. *Make use of, complement, and augment NASA satellite observational capabilities*-- the unique combination of measurements will aid interpretation of several variables measured by current and future NASA satellites;
2. *Cover multiple objectives spanning the range from exploratory to more refined quantification of known processes*-- the unique combination of measurements will allow a groundbreaking new view of processes important to ocean physics and biology, and it will allow separation and quantification of the role of several well-known physical processes in vertical transport;
3. *Complement current projects in the NASA Earth Science Research Program*-- the project addresses questions that are central to interests and activities of many NASA projects, including the SWOT Science Team, the Ocean Vector Wind Science Team, the Ocean Surface Topography Science Team, the Physical Oceanography Program, the Ocean Biology and Biogeochemistry Program, and the NASA PACE and EXPORTS field programs;
4. *Contribute to planning for future satellite observations*-- the 2017 *Decadal Survey for Earth Science and Applications from Space* recommended consideration of a Doppler scatterometer Earth System Explorer mission (likely to be based on DopplerScatt); the proposed activities will also complement and help inform SWOT cal/val activities;
5. *Contribute to enhanced Earth system models*-- the project will provide badly needed measurements to test the fidelity of rapidly evolving capabilities for numerical simulation of ocean physics and ocean-atmosphere interaction across a range of scales, and it will dramatically advance our quantitative understanding of the relationship between surface convergence/divergence, vertical transports, and primary productivity.

3.1 Science Goals and Objectives

This is a proposal to test the hypothesis that submesoscale ocean dynamics make important contributions to vertical exchange in the upper ocean. This will require coordinated application of newly-developed in situ and remote sensing techniques to provide an unprecedented view of the dynamical transition in upper-ocean circulation between the mesoscale and submesoscale and the associated physics contributing to vertical transport in the upper ocean.

To test the hypothesis that submesoscale ocean dynamics make important contributions to vertical exchange in the upper ocean, we have set these science goals:

1. **Goal: Quantitatively measure the three-dimensional structure of the submesoscale features responsible for vertical exchange.**
2. **Goal: Quantify the role of air-sea interaction and surface forcing in the dynamics and vertical velocity of submesoscale variability.**
3. **Goal: Understand the relation between the velocity (and other surface properties) measured by remote sensing at the surface and that within and just below the surface boundary layer.**
4. **Goal: Examine vertical transport processes at submesoscales to mesoscales.**

3.1.1 Goal 1: Quantitatively measure the three-dimensional structure of the submesoscale features responsible for vertical exchange

How does this goal help address the hypothesis?

Model studies (Fig. 3.2) and limited observations (Fig. 3.4) indicate that submesoscale vertical exchange is concentrated near km-scale fronts and eddies. High-resolution simulations have outpaced our observational capabilities, but observational techniques have matured rapidly over the past decade. The proposed investigation will make a comprehensive set of measurements of the dynamical variables needed to validate and discriminate between the high-resolution simulations.

What needs to be done to achieve this goal and why?

Wide-swath Doppler scatterometry (DopplerScatt) aircraft remote sensing is the centerpiece of the observation strategy. By measuring *surface currents* at submesoscale sampling resolution (1 km) over a wide area (100 km) on a daily basis, it will allow the in-situ components to be targeted at the important frontal features, while providing spatial context for these measurements. The key measurement is *current gradients*, from which vorticity, divergence and strain can be calculated, with an accuracy of $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1} = 0.2f$ at 1 km sampling, sufficient to resolve the typical frontal values. In particular, mass conservation and the incompressibility of water ensure that the horizontal current divergence equals the vertical derivative of vertical velocity and thus links the surface current measurements to vertical transport. Simultaneously, DopplerScatt will measure *wind speed*, which is the most important component of atmospheric forcing and a key determinant of frontal structure. Accuracy of about 1.5 m s^{-1} will resolve the typical $3\text{-}10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ wind speeds.

Sea surface temperature and ocean color from aircraft remote sensing provide critical *targeting* information on submesoscale frontal features, which will have strong gradients in both SST and color, and thus compliment Doppler Scatterometry. The observations in Fig. 3.5 were targeted in this way. Observations should *coincide with scatterometry* imaging to 1 hour, allowing velocity and SST/Color data to be aligned to much better than 1 km for typical currents of 0.1 m s^{-1} . SST resolution of better than 0.05°C at 100m horizontal scale will resolve the typical 0.5°C temperature difference across 5 km fronts while showing their internal structure. Similarly, Chlorophyll concentration resolution of 0.05 mg m^{-3} will resolve frontal differences of 0.5 mg m^{-3} .

Ocean vertical velocity is a central focus of this program and must be measured. Two approaches will provide redundancy and different space-time sampling. First, Lagrangian floats with ADCPs (Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler) have a demonstrated ability to directly measure *vertical velocity* associated with submesoscale vertical exchange at fronts (Fig. 3.5). *Float location* to an accuracy of 300 m several times per hour is necessary to place these measurements in proper context. Second, an array of 4 Wave Gliders, autonomous surface craft, spaced in a nominal 1 km square, and carrying downward looking ADCPs, will measure *divergence as a function of depth* from depths of a few meters to about 70 m. Integrating this divergence from its surface value, will yield continuous profiles of vertical velocity. Divergence accuracy of better than $2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, will resolve typical 1 km divergences of 10^{-4} s^{-1} . This same array will measure vertical vorticity and strain, also important frontal parameters, with similar accuracy.

Ocean horizontal velocity, temperature and salinity on a *range of scales* are needed to place vertical velocity measurements in a proper *context*. Although theory and models predict that submesoscale vertical exchange occurs within specific frontal features, the details of these features, and thus the magnitude of the exchange, vary with details of model physics. To understand this physics, and properly model it, we need to measure the structure of both the *submesoscale* features and the larger *mesoscale* features in which they are embedded. Two sampling schemes will be used.

First, the submesoscale hydrographic and velocity fields will be measured by rapid *shipboard surveys* following a Lagrangian float, an approach that has been demonstrated to yield successful measurements of submesoscale structures even in strong currents (D’Asaro et al. 2011, 2018; Thomas et al. 2015). The ship will carry an ADCP to measure velocity and a towed profiling probe, measuring temperature and salinity. These will provide a survey resolution of 1 km, a span of 5 km, a depth of 100m, and repeat every 1 to 2 hours. Previous work demonstrates that this resolution and standard oceanographic sensors with temperature and salinity accuracies of 0.005 C and 0.01 g kg⁻¹ will be sufficient, as will a standard RDI 300 kHz ADCP with accuracies of ~0.01 m s⁻¹ with 60 s averaging. Second, the mesoscale will be measured using an *array of autonomous profiling Seagliders* surveying a surrounding 25 km region, repeating a survey every two days with the spatial resolution of 5 km. These will measure temperature and salinity to a depth of 1,000 m. The greater depth is needed to capture the deeper mesoscale structures. Velocity will be measured from an ADCP on the Seagliders (Todd et al., 2017) and *mixing rates* from standard temperature and velocity microstructure sensors.

3.1.2 Goal 2: Quantify the role of air-sea interaction and surface forcing in the dynamics and vertical velocity of submesoscale variability

How does this goal help address the hypothesis?

Extensive model and observational studies highlight a variety of ways by which air-sea interaction can induce horizontal divergence of surface currents and thus force vertical velocities: The wind stress can be modified by oceanic SST and velocity gradients (Dewar and Flierl, 1987; Fairall et al., 1996; Chelton et al., 2004; O’Neill et al. 2005) while the resulting convergence of the ocean Ekman layer can be modified by surface vorticity (Stern, 1965; McGillicuddy et al., 2007; 2008). At submesoscales, these effects increase in magnitude and other phenomena also appear: Frontal structure is strongly affected by the relative direction of the wind with ‘downfront’ Ekman transports sharpening the fronts and inducing vertical exchange while ‘upfront’ transports slump the front and stratify the upper ocean (Thomas 2005). Surface waves, the ultimate mediators of air-sea momentum exchange, can be strongly modulated at fronts, suggesting that even the basic formulation of air-sea exchange in terms of simple bulk coefficients may break down at sufficiently small scales. Thus, an understanding of submesoscale structure and vertical velocity requires that air-sea interaction parameters be measured simultaneously with the other submesoscale measurements.

What needs to be done to achieve this goal and why?

As a scatterometer, DopplerScatt will measure backscatter intensity, and thus *surface wind vectors*, on the same scales as surface velocity, providing an unprecedented new opportunity to examine submesoscale modulation of wind stress. Interpretation of these data requires additional measurements: First, local measurement of *standard bulk flux parameters* (SST, wind, air temperature, humidity, solar radiation and downwelling infrared radiation). These measurements will be made on the research vessel using standard instrumentation and at least two Wave Gliders. These platforms will repeatedly survey across submesoscale features thereby measuring their submesoscale variations for comparison with DopplerScatt data. Second, *directional surface wave spectra* will be measured from an airplane-mounted Lidar (Melville et al. 2016) using the methods described in Lenain and Melville (2017). The spectra will resolve surface wave wavenumber spectra for wavelengths from 100’s of m to 10’s of cm, and thus span both the equilibrium and saturation ranges important for wave breaking and momentum transfer. The same aircraft will measure *wave breaking rates* using IR and visual imaging techniques to characterize the foam distributions, a well-

established technique (Deike et al., 2017). Additional surface wave spectral measurements will be made from the Wave Gliders with a minimum resolution of a few meters wavelength.

3.1.3 Goal 3: Understand the relation between the horizontal and vertical velocity measured by remote sensing at the surface and that within and just below the surface boundary layer

How does this goal help address the hypothesis?

Existing models and observations indicate the potential for substantial differences between the velocities measured by DopplerScatt, sampling the top few centimeters, and the boundary layer currents in the top tens of meters that feed submesoscale and mesoscale vertical velocity. These differences are due both to the near surface shear and to the average velocity gradients due to surface waves, i.e. the Stokes drift shear. Thus, interpretation of the DopplerScatt velocity measurements requires that we understand their relationship to deeper velocities.

What needs to be done to achieve this goal and why?

Several *dense arrays of surface drifters* will measure surface velocity in the top 60 cm of the ocean. These will provide a bridge from the centimeter-depth measurements of DopplerScatt to the deeper measurements from the various ADCPs. By deploying ~50 drifters at once over a roughly 10 km wide region, a range of horizontal scales and oceanographic conditions will be measured allowing the transfer function from DopplerScatt to the deeper velocities to be addressed as a function of depth, oceanographic conditions and horizontal scale. DopplerScatt velocity measurements will be aligned with the measurements from the drifters, Wave Gliders and ship and their relationships investigated. Away from fronts, the differences should depend primarily on the surface wave properties, the wind stress and near-surface density stratification. These relationships will be addressed first. Within submesoscale fronts, additional strong near surface shears will occur, associated both with the geostrophic shear of the front, its likely strong vertical density gradient, and the resulting unbalanced velocities. Investigation of these more poorly understood phenomenon may require comparisons with high-resolution numerical simulations.

3.1.4 Goal 4: Examine vertical transport processes at submesoscales to mesoscales.

How does this goal help address the hypothesis?

Vertical transport occurs when vertical velocity w aligns with a transported scalar C so that the product $\langle w'C' \rangle$ is nonzero. (Here the primes represent the perturbations from the mean, which is denoted by angle brackets). Hence, when warm water aligns with downwelling, heat is transported downward. We will estimate these fluxes, primarily for heat and chlorophyll, over a range of scales, thereby assessing the importance of submesoscale fluxes. Measuring vertical fluxes is a challenging goal, but even partial progress will be an important advance.

What needs to be done to achieve this goal and why?

We propose *remote sensing proxies for vertical velocity and flux* made possible by the unique observations. Surface velocity divergence D , measured by DopplerScatt, equals $-\partial W/\partial z$, the vertical derivative of vertical velocity. We will form proxies for vertical velocity $W_D = D h$, where h is a vertical length scale, and for flux $\langle W_D C \rangle$, where C is temperature, chlorophyll, or other biogeochemical properties, such as particulate organic carbon (POC), measured by aircraft remote sensing. We will form estimates of h by, first, combining the in situ measurements of W with DopplerScatt estimates of D , and second, by directly evaluating h in numerical models. Given a recipe for h , we will evaluate the flux proxy using our aircraft measurements, paying particular attention to its statistical stability, convergence and sensitivity to instrumental noise. We will make parallel evaluations using numerical models, both as a reality check on the proxy and a test of the

model accuracy. We will assess the *importance of the submesoscale*, our primary hypothesis, by comparing this proxy with Omega equation estimates of vertical velocity and flux (Pallàs-Sanz et al. 2010) from the mesoscale surveys, with the small-scale turbulent flux estimates from the Seagliders, and by directly examining the contributions of different horizontal scales to the flux proxies.

3.2 Baseline and Threshold Science Requirements

Science Goals 1 and 3 would be achieved by meeting these Threshold Science Requirements:

- 10-day pilot campaign with regular DopplerScatt overflights (several multi-hour data collection periods), supported by surface drifter deployments and vertical profiles of velocity gradients (vorticity, divergence and strain) with 1-km sampling at one location.
- One 14-day Intensive Operating Period during fall or spring with at least 7 DopplerScatt flights to map a 50-by-100 km region, at least 5 matching SST and ocean color scenes from PRISM, 7 glider mesoscale surveys spanning 25 km with a resolution of 2 days and 5 km, and 3 Lagrangian submesoscale feature surveys spanning 5 km and lasting 3 days with a resolution of 2 hours and 1 km. All surveys measure temperature, salinity, velocity and optics. Submesoscale surveys also measure Lagrangian surface and subsurface trajectories, vertical velocity and profiles of velocity gradients (vorticity, divergence and strain) based on 1 km sampling.

All four Science Goals would be achieved by meeting these additional Baseline Science Requirements:

- Increase duration of Intensive Operating Period to 25 days, in order to increase the number of expected submesoscale realizations to 6.
- Add one additional Intensive Operating Period in the opposite season (fall or spring) to obtain data under different mesoscale, wind, and stratification conditions.

The Threshold Mission provides a viable option for descoping and would reduce costs considerably, because it would reduce flight and ship time by 50% and also considerably reduce data processing and analysis costs.

4.0 Science Implementation

The nominal study site is offshore of San Francisco (Fig. 1.1). There will be a 10-day pilot campaign late in Year 1 (April 2020), and there will be two 25-day intensive operations periods (IOPs) in Years 2-3 (in April 2021 and September 2021).

4.1 Science Traceability Matrix

Science Hypothesis	Science Goals	Scientific Measurement Requirements			Instrument Performance	Mission Functional Requirements	
		Required observable	Required space/time sampling	Required accuracy			
<i>Submesoscale ocean dynamics make important contributions to vertical exchange of climate and biological variables in the upper ocean</i>	Goal 1: Quantitatively measure the three-dimensional structure of the submesoscale features responsible for vertical exchange	Horizontal velocity field at ocean surface	H: 2 km, >50km x 100km; T: daily, >10d	Resolve gradients of 4e-5 s ⁻¹ Equals 0.08 m s ⁻¹ over 2 km	DopplerScatt: 0.0086 m s ⁻¹ over 2 km Surface Drifters: 0.05 m s ⁻¹ in 10 ms ⁻¹ wind	Region of Interest A region with active submesoscale processes that has been studied and modelled in the past to enable comparisons of field data to modelled results. Deployment Area Measure submesoscale dynamics in an area easily accessible by ships and airborne instruments. Temporal Sampling Resolve temporal variability to identify and separate the dynamical processes of interest using sustained measurements in the deployment area over periods of days. Operations Concept Airborne and in-situ observations are conducted on the same day to directly measure vertical velocity to be associated with remotely sensed surface velocity. Additionally, radar, SST and ocean color data are collected within 1 hour to allow for temporal and spatial alignment. Radar current data collected over wide areas on a daily basis provides spatial context for the in-situ measurements.	
		Surface Chlorophyll		Resolve 0.05 mg m ⁻³ differences			PRISM: +/- 30% in the concentration range of 0.01-10 mg m ⁻³ in optically deep waters
		Ocean Temperature: SST Mesoscale Submesoscale	H: 2 km, >50km x 100km; T: daily, >10d H: 5km, 25km; V: 5m, 1000m; T: 2 days, >10d H: 1km, 5km /5m; V: 5m/150m; T: 2 hrs, >10d	0.05°C 0.01°C 0.01°C	MOSES/MASS Error: 0.01°C Spatial resolution: <1m - 10m Wave gliders w UCTD: 0.01°C; Research vessel: 0.01°C		
		Ocean salinity Mesoscale Submesoscale	As above	0.01 g kg ⁻¹	Seagliders: 0.01 g kg ⁻¹		
		Horizontal velocity: Mesoscale Submesoscale Gradients	As above H: 1 location, 1 km spacing V: 4m, 100m; T: 30s, >10d	0.01 m s ⁻¹ 0.01 m s ⁻¹ 2e-5 s ⁻¹	Seagliders w ADCP: 0.01 m s ⁻¹ Ocean vessel w ADCP: 0.01 m s ⁻¹ Gliders in 1km sq array: 2e-5 s ⁻¹ , (0.02 m s ⁻¹ over 1 km) 2m bins to 100m		
		Vertical Velocity Point Profile	T: 30s, >10 d V: 2m, 20m, T: 60s	0.003 m s ⁻¹ 0.003 ms ⁻¹	Lagrangian float: 0.001 m s ⁻¹ ADCP on Lagrangian float: 0.002 m s ⁻¹		
		Turbulent mixing rate	H: 5km, 25km; V: 5m, 1000m; T: 2 days, >10d	TKE dissipation rate noise level <1e-10 W/kg	Seagliders w temperature and velocity microstructure sensors: Noise level <1e-12 W/kg		
	Goal 3: Understand the relation between velocity measured by remote sensing at the surface and that within and just below the surface boundary layer	Horizontal velocity field: ocean surface & profiles	As above	As above	As above		
	Surface wind vectors	H: 2 km, >50km x 100km; T: daily, >10d	< 1.5 m/s	DopplerScatt: 1m/s; in-situ: 1m/s			
	Surface wave breaking; Directional wave spectra	H: 5 km, 50km x 100km; T: daily, >10d	Resolve wave breaking kinematics for wave speeds > 1m/s; Resolve wavelengths from 100's m to <1 m	MASS imagery spatial resolution: 0.05 - 0.5m Vert. accuracy: 2-4cm per individual lidar measurement Wave glider dir. wave sensor: 10 cm rms error			
	In addition to Threshold Mission goals, Baseline Mission contains the following						
	Goal 2: Quantify the role of air-sea interaction and surface forcing in the dynamics and vertical velocity of submesoscale variability	Surface solar radiation	H: point meas. OK; T: 2 hrs	bias<15 W/m ²	Radiometers on ship/gliders: bias<10 W/m ²		Region of Interest and Deployment Area Same as Threshold Mission Temporal Sampling In addition to the Threshold Mission, resolve seasonal variability of submesoscale dynamics by sampling the region of interest in different seasons to obtain data under different mesoscale, wind, and stratification conditions. Quantify evolution of submesoscale features using sustained measurements over several weeks. Operations Concept Same as Threshold Mission
		Surface downward IR radiation	H: point meas. OK; T: 2 hrs H: 5 km; T: 2 hrs				
		Air temperature & humidity	Temperature: 0.25°C; Humidity: 4%	Wave gliders: Temperature: 0.2°C; Humidity: 2%			
		Surface wind vectors	H: 2 km, >50km x 100km; T: daily, >10d	1.5 m/s	DopplerScatt: 1m/s; in-situ: 1m/s		
Surface wave breaking; Directional wave spectra		H: 5 km, 50km x 100km; T: daily, >10d	Resolve wave breaking kinematics for wave speeds > 1m/s; Resolve wavelengths from 100's m to <1 m	MASS imagery spatial resolution: 0.05 - 0.5m Vert. accuracy: 2-4cm per individual lidar measurement Wave glider dir. wave sensor: 10 cm rms error			
Goal 4: Examine vertical transport processes at submesoscales to mesoscales	SST; Chlorophyll and Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) co-located with velocity; supporting surface/subsurface data	H: 5 km; V: 5 m; T: 2-24 hrs	Chlorophyll: 0-20 mg m ⁻³ POC: 10-1000 mg m ⁻³ *Values shown are based on MODIS-Aqua April and September monthly climatology	PRISM Chlorophyll: +/- 30% MASS Chlorophyll: +/- 50%	in the concentration range of 0.01-10 mg m ⁻³ in optically deep waters		
				POC: RMSD 30% in the concentration range of 10-1000 mg m ⁻³			

4.2 Investigation approach

We will use measurements from a novel combination of platforms and instruments, along with data analysis and modeling, to test the hypothesis that submesoscale ocean dynamics make important contributions to vertical exchange in the upper ocean. The experiment will collect simultaneous measurements using several airborne instruments (Table 1.1), including the NASA DopplerScatt instrument, the NASA PRISM instrument, the SIO MASS instrument and the UCLA MOSES instrument. In conjunction with the airborne measurements, in situ data will be obtained using surface drifters, wave-propelled autonomous vehicles (Wave Gliders), Lagrangian floats that follow the 3D flow, vertically profiling autonomous underwater vehicles (Seaglidors), and a research vessel. These measurements will be complemented with satellite observations of SSH, winds, SST, and ocean color.

4.2.1 Site selection rationale

The submesoscale dynamical processes of interest vary regionally. We selected an operations area offshore of San Francisco because:

- (1) It is in a region that has been a focus area for numerous pioneering observational and modeling studies of submesoscale dynamics (e.g., Capet et al., 2008a,b,c; Pallàs-Sanz et al., 2010a,b; Johnston et al., 2011) and thus has already been well characterized, both in observations and simulations.
- (2) It is logistically and operationally convenient (near NASA Armstrong Flight Research Center and the NASA Ames Research Center, in a region not subject to US Navy airspace restrictions, close to major US seaports).
- (3) The operations area includes the nominal site for cal/val activities for the SWOT satellite mission, and includes a crossover diamond of the SWOT fast-repeat orbit (a coarse 1-day repeat ground track that will be used for about 180 days during commissioning and cal/val phases). The proposed measurements are complementary to the ones being discussed for SWOT cal/val and would help to address questions about how internal waves and submesoscale variability will appear in SWOT data.

4.2.2 Campaign timing rationale

We are targeting April 2020 for the pilot campaign and April 2021 and September 2021 for the major campaigns, called Intensive Operations Periods. The timing is motivated by the following factors:

- (1) Upper-ocean fronts are most prevalent in the region in July-October and least prevalent in March-April (Castelao et al., 2006).
- (2) The surface mixed layer is deep in March-April and shallow in September, providing seasonal contrast.
- (3) Two state-of-the-art ocean model simulations used for studying submesoscale variability exhibit qualitative disagreement in the strength of the seasonal cycle of submesoscale variability at the study site (Section 3 and Figure 3.2).
- (4) Fog, which will obscure many of the aircraft remote-sensing measurements, is minimal in September and April.
- (5) We are scheduling a full year between the pilot and the first major campaign so that we can fully analyze the data from the pilot campaign and intercompare data from different platforms. This will ensure that there is enough time to identify and address any issues with instrument or platform performance or interoperability.
- (6) Although it is not a driving factor for campaign timing, the nominal launch date for SWOT is April 2021 (the time of the first IOP), and the fast-repeat orbit is scheduled to extend

through September 2021 (the time of the second IOP). A slip of the SWOT launch would not compromise the proposed investigation in any way.

4.2.2 Aircraft sampling plan

We will conduct three types of aerial surveys: (1) *Synoptic surveys of the 75 km x 300 km nominal experiment domain (Figs. 1.1 and 3.2) by DopplerScatt*, which can cover the region once in one flight sortie and is unaffected by fog or cloud cover. The purpose of these surveys, needed at least once during each campaign, is to identify interesting submesoscale features that can be targeted by the in situ measurements. DopplerScatt's near-real-time data products can guide campaign execution and add a broad context for the 25 km Intensive Operations Region (IOR), described in 4.2.3. (2) *Fast sampling surveys of the IOR designed to characterize the temporal evolution of the submesoscale field, together with internal waves and tides*. For this mode, the faster airplanes will select an optimal azimuth angle for sampling (e.g., to mitigate sun glint or maximize time over the site) and overfly the IOR region back and forth on 100 km-long tracks, which take between 10 (PRISM) to 20 (DopplerScatt/MOSES) minutes, including turns. The horizontal separation between the tracks will be varied to cover the full area (PRISM) or mitigate nadir gaps (DopplerScatt). The full area will be covered at least once in less than one hour. The slower and narrower-swath MASS platform will target the IOR only, each leg taking less than 10 minutes, so that the entire IOR is covered in about 2 hours. In a single sortie, the IOR will be covered about 4 times by all instruments. (3) *Fast-Synoptic sampling of a rectangular 50 km square centered on the IOR*. The purpose of this sampling pattern is to (a) add a synoptic context to the IOR; and, (b) to collect data in a checkerboard pattern with perpendicular sets of tracks for MASS and PRISM. For DopplerScatt, covering the area will mitigate the 2 km nadir gaps apparent in Fig. 3.6 and homogenize the error structure. For MASS, selecting a checkerboard pattern will allow for swaths collected along and across the wave or front direction, which will improve data products. PRISM will overfly the area in a lawn-mower pattern whose azimuth angle is selected to minimize sun glint. The pattern will image the larger 50 km area twice per sortie for each instrument. These collection modes can be run on any given day: the mode selection will be based on the analysis of near-real-time airborne and in situ data, as well as weather and wave conditions.

4.2.3 In situ sampling plan

For in situ measurements, we will operate in an Intensive Operations Region (IOR) about 25 km on a side, centered on a strong submesoscale front, or eddy. This feature will be located using 100-km scale DopplerScatt, SST and ocean color aircraft surveys. As outlined in Section 3.2.1 and shown in Figure 4.1, the sampling will consist of a nested grid of measurements spanning scales from 25 km to 1 km using multiple autonomous platforms and a ship.

Figure 4.1 In-situ sampling plan for IOP. A nested sampling grid spans a range of scales from 25 km to 1 km centered on a submesoscale front using a combination of autonomous platforms and a research vessel. The sampling patterns of different platforms will overlap, despite being separated in this illustration for clarity.

Moving from the largest scale to the smallest, the *mesoscale* will be sampled by an array of 4 Seagliders each transiting the 25 km region along a racetrack pattern. Each Seaglider will repeatedly dive to 1000 m, surfacing every ~3 km along the track and traveling about 25 km per day. The array will thus map the entire region at a resolution of approximately 3 km every two days, measuring temperature, salinity, chlorophyll, velocity, and mixing rate. One Lagrangian float will be deployed away from submesoscale features and operated in an isopycnal-following mode below the base of the mixed layer, in order to measure vertical velocities associated with internal tides, internal waves and mesoscale motions.

The *submesoscale* will be sampled by the combination of a research vessel, Lagrangian floats, and Wave Gliders. One or more floats will be deployed at the front within the surface mixed layer after a preliminary survey by the research vessel. The floats will move downward with the water subducting at the front, perhaps programmed to resurface periodically. The ship will acoustically track the floats, aided by additional tracking from the gliders, and continuously survey around the float at a range of approximately 5 km using the onboard ADCP and towed Underway CTD, to measure the velocity and density fields at a resolution of about 1 km. Four Wave Gliders will form a ~1 km square array, using their onboard ADCPs to measure the vertical profiles of horizontal velocity gradients, divergence, and vorticity as they repeatedly transit across the front. Large arrays of >30 surface drifters will be deployed in a 10 km pattern spanning particularly interesting features, mapping the near-surface currents for comparison with DopplerScatt, and providing additional measurements of the surface divergence and vorticity values. Each submesoscale deployment will last a few days after which it will be redeployed at a new submesoscale feature.

Some *seawater sample analysis* efforts will also be required. Water samples will be taken from the research vessel and analyzed for chlorophyll-a, particulate and total organic carbon, dissolved oxygen and nutrients. These samples will be used for sensor calibration and drift correction, proxy building (for in situ and remote sensing) of Chl and POC. They will also be used for directly estimating nutrient and total carbon flux.

4.2.4 Pilot campaign

A pilot campaign will be conducted near the end of the first year of the project with the goals of (1) testing and improving the interoperability of measurement platforms and land-based operations, (2) conducting time-resolved aircraft flights over repeat lines to characterize space-time variability (both for dynamical understanding and for optimizing sampling during IOPs), (3) intercomparing the different measurement methods, particularly for velocity. The pilot study will include the full complement of aircraft measurements, a research vessel, the four Wave Gliders, and about 30 surface drifters. SeaGlider and Lagrangian float components are not included, both to save costs and because the APL/UW is very familiar with this type of operation. A limited version of the operations plans described above will be conducted during the pilot campaign, substituting one or more surface drifters for the Lagrangian float and paying particular attention to intercomparison of velocities and velocity gradients from DopplerScatt, the surface drifters and the Wave Gliders.

4.2.5 Intensive Operations Periods (IOPs)

There will be two month-long Intensive Operations Periods during which all assets will be deployed, one in April 2021 and one in September 2021 (with backups September 2021 and April 2022). The sampling strategy will be the same for the two IOP campaigns.

4.3 Investigation timeline

The major milestones of the investigation are depicted as a timeline in Figure 4.2. As a contingency, the timing of all three campaigns could be pushed back six months while retaining the

spring/fall campaign timing, so that the Pilot Campaign would take place in September 2020, and the IOPs would take place in September 2021 and April 2022.

Figure 4.2: Timeline of investigation, depicting major milestones of the project.

4.4 Science Team

Table 4.2. The science team includes experts in theoretical and numerical ocean modeling, oceanographic field campaigns, remote sensing, as well as members of the SWOT science, algorithm, and cal/val teams.

Team Member	Inst.	Role and Responsibilities	Qualification
Management			
J. Thomas Farrar	WHOI	Principal Investigator: Work with Science Investigation Manager, FDM team, and deputy PIs to ensure that measurements are collected as needed to address science objectives and data products are delivered.	PI on numerous oceanographic field projects; Co-chair of SPURS-2 steering committee; Member of SWOT algorithm team and cal/val team; member Ocean Surface Topography Science Team, Ocean Vector Wind Science Team, SWOT Science team
Paul Matthias	WHOI	Science Investigation Manager: Work with PI and FDM team to meet project objectives and deliverables	WHOI Sr. Program Manager with over 20 years experience managing large (>\$25M/year) ocean engineering Programs.
Science Data Analysis & Modeling			
Eric D'Asaro	UW-APL	Deputy PI for Science Data Analysis: primary responsibility for data analysis and publication; co-lead for Lagrangian floats	PI on numerous oceanographic field projects; longstanding interest in and pioneer of techniques to measure vertical velocity; Member of National Academy of Sciences
Amala Mahadevan	WHOI	co-I; providing input on process modeling and interpretation of optical/biogeochemical measurements	Co-chair of ONR ASIRI and Calypso Departmental Research Initiatives focused on submesoscale dynamics
Melissa Omand	URI	co-I; primary responsibility for bio-optical/biogeochemical measurements on Wave Gliders, bio-optical proxy building and calibration through water sampling and analysis.	PI responsible for bio-optics measurements on various major campaigns including NASA EXPORTS, ONR ASIRI and MISO-BOB, and NSF projects.
Dudley Chelton	OSU	co-I; working with OSU team especially analysis of remote sensing to address air-sea interaction goal (focus on vorticity modification of wind-driven upwelling)	35+ years in ocean remote sensing, especially altimetry and scatterometry; specialist in mesoscale air-sea interaction
Roger Samelson	OSU	co-I; primary responsibility for OSU component, including theoretical and numerical modeling of upper ocean dynamics and local ocean-atmosphere fluxes and coupling	PI on numerous oceanographic research projects involving ocean dynamics and air-sea coupling
Larry O'Neill	OSU	co-I; working with OSU team especially analysis of remote sensing to address air-sea interaction goal (focus on SST-wind relationship)	Specialist in mesoscale air-sea interaction; member of Ocean Vector Wind Science Team
Andrew Thompson	Cal Tech	co-I; contributor to JPL modelling activities and analysis of the glider data; will contribute to the design of the mesoscale/submesoscale surveys.	Experience in analysis of high resolution model output and analysis of submesoscale dynamics from glider field campaigns.
Dimitris Menemenlis	JPL	co-I; responsible for JPL modelling activities, including an Observation System Simulation Experiment (OSSE) pre-campaign to optimize sampling strategy, (2) high-resolution regional simulations, and (3) simulations concurrent with the observational campaign	25 years experience working with general circulation models and ocean state estimation technology. Developer of Massachusetts Institute of Technology general circulation model (MITgcm) and member of the Estimating the Circulation and Climate of the Oceans (ECCO) Consortium.
James C. McWilliams	UCLA	co-I; will work with Molemaker to design and implement UCLA model simulations	40+ years experience in oceanographic observations, theory, and modeling; expert on submesoscale dynamics
In Situ Measurements			
Andrey Shcherbina	UW-APL	Deputy PI for in Situ Measurements: primary responsibility for coordination and execution of oceanographic measurements from ships and autonomous platforms; co-lead for Lagrangian floats	Lead author of one of the few existing observational studies of submesoscale vorticity and divergence (Shcherbina et al. 2013); PI on numerous observational campaigns focused on submesoscale and upper-ocean dynamics
Luc Rainville	UW-APL	co-I and Glider co-lead; responsible for coordination of the Seaglider array with other platforms. Primary responsibility for the velocity and turbulence measurements from	PI on numerous oceanographic field projects; serving on several steering committees and NASA science teams.

		Seaglidgers.	
Craig Lee	UW-APL	co-I and Glider co-lead; responsible for glider operations and for designing sampling strategies for mesoscale and sub-mesoscale surveys. Participation in analysis and interpretation of physical and biological tracer data.	PI on numerous oceanographic projects; extensive experience in glider operations and in designing sampling strategies for mesoscale and sub-mesoscale surveys.
Aircraft Measurements			
Ernesto Rodriguez	JPL	Deputy PI for Aircraft Measurements: primary responsibility for coordination and execution of aircraft campaigns. Development of higher level L3 DopplerScatt data products.	Originator of the DopplerScatt concept and DopplerScatt science lead. Multiple airborne campaigns for DopplerScatt and AirSWOT, as PI. QuikSCAT & RapidScat project scientist. Member of Ocean Vector Wind and SWOT science teams.
Dragana Perkovic-Martin	JPL	DopplerScatt Instrument Lead and co-I	PI of DopplerScatt IIP and AITT programs, led multiple airborne campaigns in collaboration with NASA Armstrong Flight Research Center
Pantazis Mouroulis	JPL	PRISM Instrument Lead and co-I	PI/Col for the development of several imaging spectrometers including PRISM. 35+ years of experience in optical instrumentation, 20+ in imaging spectroscopy.
Michelle Gierach	JPL	co-I; responsible for the validation and science analysis of PRISM-derived products; support the PRISM airborne campaign	10+ years in remote sensing; PI/Co-I/Project Scientist on several projects using PRISM. NASA EVS-2 CORAL Project Scientist.
David R. Thompson	JPL	co-I; responsible for algorithm development and refinement of PRISM-derived products; contribute to the validation and science analysis of PRISM-derived products; support the PRISM airborne campaign	10+ years in remote sensing; PI/Co-I on multiple projects using PRISM. AVIRIS Investigation Scientist. EMIT Mission Instrument Scientist and Science Team.
Jeroen Molemaker	UCLA	co-I and Infrared camera instrument Lead; Responsible for UCLA modeling using ROMS.	5+ years in remote sensing of SST. Chief scientist during CARTHE field campaign. 20 years in realistic, high resolution modelling.
Luc Lenain	SIO	co-I and MASS instrument Lead; Wave Glider co-lead; working collaboratively with Farrar to equip SIO and WHOI Wave Gliders with oceanographic and meteorological instruments.	15+ years in remote sensing and observational oceanography; Chief or lead scientist in more than 15 projects using the MASS; NASA SWOT science team member.
Ken Melville	SIO	co-I; will work with Lenain on MASS measurements and Wave Glider measurements and analysis	40+ years experience in oceanographic observations, instrumentation, theory and modeling; expert on ocean waves and air-sea interaction

4.5 Science Data

4.5.1. Airborne Data Products

DopplerScatt: During surveys, DopplerScatt produces level 0 (L0) radar/GPS-IMU data stored onboard on redundant removable disks, as well as near-real-time quick-look data of sigma0 and radial velocity images suitable for mission planning and data quality assessment. The data are then transferred to data storage servers to be processed into L1 and L2 data using post-processed GPS/IMU data. L1 data consist of geolocated conical scans of sigma0 and Doppler radial velocity, together with calibration and ancillary engineering and motion data. L2 data are geolocated, 24 km swath-based gridded data sets of surface winds and wind-corrected surface currents, as well as formal measurement errors (Rodríguez et al., 2018). Near-real-time, L0-L2 data production is fully operational and has been developed under NASA's IIP and AITT programs, and their delivery will be under responsibility of co-I Perkovic-Martin. The data are then processed in to L3 gridded data products of surface winds and currents (Rodríguez et al. 2018), surface current derivatives, as well as surface current and winds vorticity, divergence, and strain-rate (e.g., Fig. 3.6) and have been developed by co-I Rodríguez under NASA OVWST and PO funding; he will responsible for their delivery.

MASS: During surveys, MASS produces level 0 sensor data (topographic lidar, IR, visible and hyperspectral imagers) stored on onboard portable storage computer then transferred to processing and data storage servers. All MASS level 1 and 2 products are georeferenced from the aircraft to an earth coordinate frame using a Novatel SPAN-LN200, an accurate GPS-IMU to provide position and attitude data at up to 200 Hz. To produce calibrated radiance values [$\text{mW (cm}^2 \text{ sr } \mu\text{m)}^{-1}$], measurements of incoming downwelling radiation are collected using a fiber-optic downwelling

irradiance sensor (FODIS) placed atop the fuselage of the aircraft and synchronized with the hyperspectral camera. The camera system (hyperspectral and FODIS sensor) is calibrated at the SpecTIR facility prior to installation on the aircraft. Added value products, categorized as level 3, are derived through algorithms developed during the analysis and science investigation part of the project.

MOSES: MOSES uses LWIR to produce radiometric images of the sea surface temperature with a pixel resolution of 620x480 at a rate of 4 Hz. These images are synchronized with a GPS/IMU sensor, geo-referenced and averaged on a binned map with a resolution of 10m. The effects of atmospheric absorption/emission on the radiometric data are removed to 1st order by considering the atmospheric pathlength of incoming radiation for each individual pixel. A cloud detection algorithm is used, but the system can partially detect SST's underneath clouds by combining observations at different look angles as the aircraft passes over. 'First look' maps of SST will be produced in near real-time and can be used to guide in-situ observations. Examples of MOSES products are shown in D'Asaro et al. (2018).

PRISM: PRISM produces Level 0 at-sensor digital numbers that are streamed to a recording unit where the data are stored. Within the JPL science data system, these data are translated into a Level 1 geometrically corrected and calibrated radiance product, Level 2 water leaving reflectance estimate (Thompson et al. 2015), and Level 3 chlorophyll-a and particulate organic carbon (POC) estimates. Level 1 data is orthorectified and mapped to a geographic reference frame by combining data from an IMU/GPS sensor with an instrument camera model. The PRISM Level 2 algorithm is based on the (ATmospheric REMoval) ATREM formulation (Gao 2000; Gao et al. 2007), which incorporates models of aerosols and sunglint, and has been validated over a wide range of operating altitudes. Two Level 3 chlorophyll-a retrievals will be provided, including a simple multiband estimate for direct comparison with satellite retrievals (e.g., SeaWiFS OC4v6, O'Reilly et al., 1998; MODIS-Aqua OC3M) as well as a full spectroscopic retrieval of water properties using the deep water model of Lee et al. (2004). An example of the spectroscopic chlorophyll-a retrieval is shown in Fig. 4.3. POC retrievals will follow the approach of Stramski et al. (2008). PRISM chlorophyll-a and POC retrievals will be validated with in situ measurements collected during the campaign by Co-I Melissa Omand. The California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigations (CalCOFI) repeat hydrographic surveys (e.g., lines 60 and 63.3 shown in http://calcofi.org/images/maps/75-104_Station_Positions1024B.jpg) provide an additional validation source. All CalCOFI data is

publicly available and distributed at <http://calcofi.org/>.

Figure 4.3 Example of chlorophyll-a variability associated with submesoscale features from PRISM on the

NASA ER-2 in the Santa Monica Bay, California on 26 October 2015. PRISM was flown on the NASA ER-2 at 65kft, providing a swath of about 11km and spatial resolution better than 20m. Such instrument and platform specifications are proposed within this investigation.

4.5.2 In Situ Data Products

Wave Glider data: The array of wave gliders is instrumented with a suite of sensors recording level 0 data to onboard data storage. During the experiment, averaged measurements, profiles (currents, temperature) and wave spectra are sent back to shore via Iridium communication every 5-20 min (user-defined). All level 0 data are downloaded upon recovery of the Wave Gliders to compute Level 1 and 2 data products.

Drifter data: CARTHE drifter GPS positions are telemetered in real-time via the Globalstar network. A Level-1 drifter trajectory dataset will be produced at the end of each campaign.

Seaglider data: Seagliders are fully-autonomous, with mission parameters adjustable whenever the Seaglider surfaces. The gliders records the Level-0 CTD, ADCP, bio-optical and microstructure data internally. All data except the ADCP and level-0 microstructure data is telemetered to shore via Iridium uplink during surface intervals for mission control and is converted to real-time Level-1. All the data are offloaded upon recovery, and quality-controlled Level-1 datasets are also produced.

Lagrangian Float data: Lagrangian Floats are fully-autonomous, with mission parameters adjustable whenever the float surfaces. The float records the Level-0 CTD, ADCP, and bio-optics data internally. All data except the level-0 ADCP data is telemetered to shore via Iridium uplink during surface intervals for mission control and is converted to real-time Level-1. All the data are offloaded upon the recovery, and the quality-controlled Level-1 datasets are also produced.

Shipboard data: Shipboard data collection procedures vary slightly from one UNOLS vessel to another. In most cases, underway meteorological and hydrographic data are assembled into a unified Level-2 datafile on-board, with the raw Level-0 data preserved as well. Underway ADCP observations are typically processed in near-real-time with the University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System (UHDAS) that produces Level-2 data. For the Underway CTD data, Level-1 data will be available in near-real time, and a Level 2 data set, quality controlled and processed to 1-m depth bins, will be available at the end of the cruises.

4.5.4 Data Management

Level-0 to Level-3 data products and their leads are listed in Table 4.3. The PI and Science Investigation manager will be responsible for ensuring that all products are delivered to the designated NASA data center within 6 months after each campaign. PRISM and DopplerScatt data products will be processed at JPL using their associated science data systems.

Table 4.3. L0-L3 data products.

Level	Deliverable Product	Lead	Nominal Delivery Date		
			Campaign 1 (Apr 2020)	Campaign 2 (Apr 2021)	Campaign 3 (Sept 2021)
0	In situ measurements (see text)	Shcherbina	June 2020	June 2021	Nov 2021
1	In situ measurements (see text)	Shcherbina	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
1	DopplerScatt L0-L2 data (see text)	Perkovic-Martin	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
3	DopplerScatt L3 data (see text)	Rodriguez	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
1	PRISM radiance	Mouroulis	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
2	PRISM water leaving reflectance	Mouroulis	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
3	PRISM chl-a and POC	Mouroulis	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
1	MASS Georeferenced lidar point cloud; Radiance; georeferenced IR and visible imagery	Lenain	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
2	MASS bulk wave statistics; water leaving reflectance; SST maps.	Lenain	Oct 2020	Oct 2021	Mar 2022
3	MASS directional wavenumber spectra; Chl-a concentration; IR-based surface velocity; Whitecap coverage and wave breaking statistics	Lenain	Apr 2021	Apr 2022	Sept 2023

4.5.5 Data Analysis and Publication Plan

Six full-time postdoctoral investigators (‘Postdocs’) will work on the project for two years each. This is an important part of our plan to ensure that the investigation arrives at its intended end: new scientific understanding of ocean submesoscale dynamics and vertical transport, disseminated in the peer-reviewed literature. Postdocs will work full time toward realizing the investigation goals, and they are generally highly motivated to finish and publish results in a timely fashion.

Analysis will start in the first year of the project with an emphasis on mining existing ocean models and running new simulations to optimize the experimental design. Physically, we are particularly interested in understanding the detailed structure of submesoscale fronts and their relationship to vertical exchange, which will directly influence the experimental design. The experimental team also needs guidance on potential aliasing by diurnal cycling in the upper ocean, on optimal array sizes and survey patterns for the submesoscale sampling, and on the trade-offs between array size and repeated sampling for the aircraft surveys. Much of this work will be conducted by Postdocs at UCLA and JPL/CalTech, but with strong interactions between modeling efforts and the experimental team. It is expected that several publications will result from this work.

During the second and third year of the project, most of the effort will be spent on the two IOP efforts, in particular processing and understanding data from the first IOP rapidly enough so that the lessons learned can be applied to the second IOP. A Postdoc at Scripps will help with this task.

Data will be analyzed and published in years 3-5. Each experimental group will be responsible for producing level 2 data for public release and sharing with other investigators. We anticipate two data workshops per year. Analysis will be conducted by the co-Is in collaboration with three Postdocs. A 2-year Postdoc at OSU will focus on Goal 2, air-sea interaction effects, with an emphasis on diagnosing the effects of ocean vorticity, SST and currents on wind stress and induced vertical velocity in both the observations and numerical models. A 2-year Postdoc at SIO will focus on Goal 1, with an emphasis on analyzing the Wave Glider velocity data, and also on Goal 2, the modulation of wave spectra measured by MASS, by frontal processes and the resulting effects on wind stress. A 2-year Postdoc at APL/UW will focus on Goal 1, submesoscale structure, combining the in-situ products into a unified view of fronts, subduction and vertical exchange. Efforts on Goal 3 will be led by JPL, but rely heavily on collaboration with the in situ experimental teams at SIO, WHOI and APL/UW. Synthesis of these efforts toward Goal 4 will be led by the PI and Science Data Analysis Lead. We expect individual publications on each of these focused efforts and one or more joint publications describing the overall experiment and synthesizing the major results.

5.0 Investigation Implementation

We implement our investigation using airborne oceanographic and platforms and instruments that were chosen for their ability to meet our requirements with appropriate cost and risk, while providing adequate performance margins. The airborne platforms and instruments have been flown in the same configurations in past years. Integrations and tests have been performed multiple times and the crews have flown similar missions. Given the proximity of the aircraft homes to the experiment site, the logistics are straightforward. Weight and balance, power, and payload volume requirements are within platform capabilities, with appropriate margin. The investigation also employs autonomous ocean platforms and an oceanographic research vessel; these platforms and instruments have also been used extensively by the Science Team. No new technology development is required.

5.1 Measurement Platform System Capabilities

Platform System Capabilities: Table 5.1 presents mass, power, volume requirements from actual installations and appropriate instrument margins against the selected airborne platforms.

Table 5.1 (next page): DopplerScatt (DS) & MOSES NASA KA B200 801 capabilities, MASS Twin Otter capabilities and PRISM NASA ER-2 capabilities. Note that PRISM has completed two campaigns in the ER-2 configuration. When PRISM is the only instrument on board the aircraft carries ballast in order to balance the load. There will be no changes to the instrument mass/volume/power requirements for this installation.

Parameter		Mass (lb)	Volume (cu ft)	Flight altitude (ft)	Airspeed (knots)	Duration (hrs)	Power (W)
DopplerScatt & MOSES	Requirement	497	33.6	28,000	240	5	1,700
	Capability	772	205	35,000	280	6	6580
	Margin (%)	55	510	25	17	20	287
MASS	Requirement	265	10	100-6,000	100	8	600
	Capability	600	200	25,000	135	9	8,400
	Margin (%)	127	1900	>300	35	13	1,300
PRISM	Requirement	<400	fit tested	60-70,000	400-450	6	1,350
	Capability	2600	fit tested	70,000	450	8	6580
	Margin (%)	NA	NA	NA	NA	33	387

Contingency Plans: If NASA King Air (KA) B200 #801 is not available, DopplerScatt could be implemented through DOE KA B200 used during DopplerScatt Instrument Incubator Program. PRISM could be accommodated on a commercial Twin Otter at the expense of spatial coverage, or preferably on a Gulfstream-IV (G-IV) or G-V with additional integration costs. MASS could be installed in another commercially available Twin Otter DHC-6 or any other twin-engine aircraft equipped with a port hole large enough to accommodate the instrument, at the expense of spatial coverage for the latter. Finally, we are flexible in the times for our campaigns and could reschedule one entire campaign to other months subsequent, or, if need be, shift by one year using our budgets.

NPR 7900.3: The aircraft supporting PRISM and DopplerScatt are managed directly by NASA AFRC and are compliant with NPR 7900.3. Twin Otter International (TOI) is chosen to support the MASS instrument due to exceptional past performance supporting NASA work over the last 20 years (e.g. ASO, AVIRIS, CFIS, HyTES, PALS, POLSCAT, PRISM). TOI expects formal compliance with all NASA requirements prior to the start of the project but have also implemented a contingency plan using two other aircraft provider options, Airtec (<http://www.flyairtec.com/>), and the NPS/NAVY “CIRPAS” Twin Otter (Marina, CA), both compliant with NPR7900.3², in case there are delays in TOI’s certification process.

5.2 Logistics

Airborne Logistics: The airborne platforms have flown with the same instruments, and the experiment site is in easy reach of the NASA Armstrong platform base and the Ames Flight Research Center, as well as many local airports that can host the commercial Twin Otter aircraft. The organization and logistics for the airborne campaigns will follow previous deployments in the area, so the resource constraints are well known to the science team and the flight crews.

Platform Availability: Science Operations Flight Request System (SOFRS) requests have been submitted for DopplerScatt and PRISM. We have obtained a written commitment from Twin Otter International (TOI), whose customers include DOE, NASA, JPL, NOAA, and NRL. A number of NASA/JPL instruments (ASO, AVIRIS, CFIS, HyTES, PALS, POLSCAT, PRISM) have been flown by TOI in recent years. Radar licenses have been secured for DopplerScatt. Given the short distance between the experiment site and the aircraft bases, and given the fact that ocean data do not need to be collected in a short time window, accommodating airborne platform availability to any changes needed in the schedule will be straightforward.

²Airtec is expected to be NPR7900.3 compliant by July 2018. The NAVY/NPS “CIRPAS” Twin Otter, is already NPR7900.3 compliant, per NASA AFSRB.

Table 5.2: Data products and accuracies for DopplerScatt, PRISM, and MASS instruments.

Instrument	Parameter		Requirement	Instrument Performance	Drivers/Comments
DopplerScatt	Currents	Surface current precision	0.09 m/s over 5 km	0.0215 m/s over 5 km	Primary synoptic measure of sub-mesoscale currents. Used to compute divergence, gradients.
		Winds	Wind direction accuracy	< 30 deg	< 20 deg
	Wind Speed accuracy		1.5 m/s	1 m/s	
	Spatial	Ground resolution	< 5 km	< 1 km (200m posting)	Allows for viewing of surface processes well within the submesoscale range.
Swath		50x100 km per sortie	24 km (>50x600 km per sortie)	Wide swath coverage allows for characterization of surface processes, and, in particular, derivative fields at the submesoscale. A single sortie per day is sufficient to meet overall spatial extent requirements.	
PRISM	Spectral	Range	400-1000 nm	350-1050 nm	Visible/near-infrared spectral range needed to derive chlorophyll-a and biogeochemical properties.
		Sampling	10 - 15 nm	2.83 nm	10-15 nm is the MODIS-equivalent bandwidth
	Spatial	Ground resolution	<= 200 m	< 20 m	As close to DopplerScatt spatial resolution (200m) as possible; ER-2 platform provides the highest altitude (65kft) and thereby greatest swath and ground resolution
		Swath	5 km	< 11 km	Maximize areal coverage; capture features of interest on the order of 100m-10km; ER-2 platform provides the highest altitude (65kft) and thereby greatest swath and ground resolution
MASS - LIDAR (Riegl Q680i waveform topographic scanning lidar)	Directional wave spectra and statistics	Accuracy	10 cm per lidar pulse	2-4 cm per lidar pulse ³	To characterize the evolution of surface wave wavenumber spectra for wavelengths from 100's m to 10's cm, across submesoscale features, and to compute Stokes drift.
		Sea surface height	Accuracy	0.5 cm over 10 km	1 cm @ 1 km; 0.3 cm @ 10km wavelength
	Spatial	Ground resolution	< 5 m	0.2-1 m	Need to resolve directional wave spectra down to submeter scales to characterize the transition from saturation to equilibrium range
		Swath	>100 m	100-2000 m	Swath wide enough to ensure sufficient directional resolution for the wave spectrum computation
MASS - Infrared Cameras (FLIR SC67000HS and SC6000)	Sea Surface Temperature	Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference	0.1 K	<0.035 K	To identify submesoscale frontal features associated with strong gradients of SST and compute surface currents
	Spectral	Range	8-9- μ m	7.5–10.5- μ m and 8.0–9.2- μ m	
	Spatial	Ground resolution	<10 m	0.3-5 m	Ground resolution and image size are function of flight altitude; the latter will be adjusted based on the properties of the targets of interest
MASS - Hyperspectral Imager (SPECIM Kestrel)	Spectral	Range	400-900 nm	400–990 nm	Visible/near-infrared spectral range needed to derive chlorophyll-a and biogeochemical properties; To identify submesoscale frontal features associated with strong gradients of ocean color.
		Sampling	10-15 nm	1.75 to 7 nm	10-15 nm is the MODIS-equivalent bandwidth
	Spatial	Ground resolution	<=200	0.1-1 m	Ground resolution and image size are function of flight altitude; the latter will be adjusted based on the properties of the targets of interest
		Swath		200-2000 m	
MASS - Visible Imagers	Whitecap coverage and breaking statistics	Spectral Range	Visible	Visible	Visible range needed to identify whitecap coverage and wave breaking rates
		Sampling frequency	>2 Hz	10 Hz	Selected camera framerate is sufficient to characterize whitecap kinematics assuming 100kts aircraft survey speed but can be increased up to 100Hz as needed
	Spatial	Ground resolution	<10 m	0.05-1 m	Ground resolution and image size are function of flight altitude; the latter will be adjusted based on the properties of the targets of interest
		Swath	>100 m	400-3000 m	
MOSES (FLIR A6750SC SLS)	Sea Surface Temperature	Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference	0.05 K	0.01 K	To identify submesoscale frontal features associated with strong gradients of SST.
	Spatial	Ground resolution	100 m	13 m	Ground resolution and image size are function of flight altitude; the latter will be adjusted based on the properties of the targets of interest
		Swath		8.4 km	

³ Sufficient to resolve wavelengths from 100's m to <1 m scales.

In situ measurement logistics: In situ observations and autonomous asset deployment will be conducted from an ocean-class UNOLS vessel. A University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS) ship time request has been submitted for the oceanographic research vessel, *R/V Sally Ride*. The ship's home port is San Diego, CA, minimizing transit costs. The request was for a total of 79 days, which includes time at sea to complete the proposed work, as well as days for mobilization, demobilization, and transit from remote ports. The *R/V Sally Ride* or other suitable vessel will be available for the work (see UNOLS Letter of Commitment).

5.3 Instrumentation

Table 4.1 shows the traceability from requirements to measurement accuracies. The instruments below meet these accuracy requirements.

5.3.1 DopplerScatt

Rationale: NASA's DopplerScatt instrument (Rodriguez et al., 2018) provides simultaneous measurements of ocean vector winds and surface currents estimates over a 24-km swath. The surface currents are used to compute surface convergence and vorticity. Winds are used to investigate air-sea interaction and to estimate the wind-driven current component.

Instrument Description: DopplerScatt uses a pencil-beam mechanically scanning antenna that measures surface radar cross sections and radial Doppler velocities that are processed to estimate ocean vector winds and currents concurrently. The instrument operates at Ka-band (35.75 GHz), allowing for a compact antenna accommodation using waveguide slot array technology (22 cm diameter) protected by the RF-transparent radome (Fig. 5-1). The antenna rotation enables wide swath coverage (24 km when flying at 28 kft) as well as looks in multiple azimuth directions allowing the recovery of **vector** winds and surface currents at 200 m spatial resolution. Unlike traditional scatterometers, the radar operates coherently allowing for Doppler measurements of the relative velocity between the platform and the surface. DopplerScatt includes a precision IMU coupled with the Applanix GPS receiver which enables accurate motion compensation and removal of the platform velocity for retrieval of the surface velocity component.

Figure 5-1: DopplerScatt Ka-band radar system is modular, compact and easy to install.

DopplerScat was developed under NASA Earth Science and Technology Office (ESTO) Instrument Incubator Program (IIP) and NASA Airborne Instrument Technology Transition (AITT). It has participated in four ocean campaigns that have allowed the characterization of the system error budget and calibration process (Rodriguez et al., 2018).

Data Products and Performance Characteristics: The measurement of radar winds using pencil beam scatterometry has a long history dating back to the QuikSCAT instrument. Unlike QuikSCAT, DopplerScatt uses Ka-band instead of Ku-band. A geophysical model function (GMF) at Ka-band, to translate backscatter into wind has been developed by Yurovsky et al. (2016) and Rodriguez et al. (2018), allowing the generation of vector wind products estimated at 200 m resolution as shown in Rodriguez et al. (2018). DopplerScatt wind data have been compared against buoys (Rodriguez et al. 2018) and shown to have a wind speed accuracy on the order of 1 m/s and a direction standard deviation better than 20 deg, which is similar or better performance to that achieved by QuikSCAT. The principle of using radar phase to estimate surface currents has a long history (e.g., Goldstein et al. 1989; Romeiser and Thompson, 2000; Frasier and Camps, 2001; Chapron et al., 2005) and has been proposed as the basis for ESA (Ardhuin et al. 2017), NASA

(Rodriguez et al. 2016) and Chinese (Bao et al. 2015) spaceborne concepts. DopplerScatt inverts surface current vectors on a 200 m grid, and sample products are described in detail in Rodriguez et al. (2018). The errors calculating the surface current derivatives at high resolution are driven by the random noise in the measurement, while another component of the velocity error budget, which is driven by the wind, does not vary significantly over a kilometer scales, and can be neglected in the analysis of surface current derivatives required by this proposal. Rodriguez et al. (2018) have conducted a detailed analysis of the random errors for the velocity components and the estimates from actual retrievals. Aside from a small strip along the nadir track, the random errors for 200-m resolution velocity retrievals are smaller than 15 cm/s, and often significantly smaller. Since the random errors decrease with the square root of the number of independent samples, the random error after averaging to 2 km pixels will be $\ll 2$ cm/s, leading to the accuracy shown in the science traceability matrix.

Figure 5.2 (left) DopplerScatt accommodation schematic on the NASA King Air B200; (right) DopplerScatt mounted on the B200 belly.

Platform Integration Characteristics: DopplerScatt is designed for integration into NASA AFRC King Air B200 (#801) (Fig. 5.1-5.2). There are three components: 1) radar mounted in the nadir forward port of the B200; 2) in-cabin electronics rack; and 3) Welch power distribution rack in the rear of the aircraft. Integration requires a single day. Only one instrument operator is required in flight. Calibration data are acquired during the deployment by collecting data on exactly opposite headings of a single data collection line. De-installation of the sensor requires less than a day.

5.3.2 PRISM

Rationale: PRISM provides hyperspectral measurements of radiances (for estimation of near-surface chlorophyll and other biogeochemical properties) calibrated to NIST standards that exceed the MODIS-equivalent measurement requirements in the STM table. Mounting on the ER-2 aircraft guarantees full scene coverage at a spatial resolution exceeding the science requirements.

Instrument Description: PRISM (Mouroulis et al. 2014) has been developed to specifically address the requirements of airborne coastal ocean research. PRISM covers the 350-1050 nm range with a 2.83 nm sampling and a 31° field of view. The Dyson spectrometer design provides for high SNR, uniformity of response, and low polarization sensitivity, while the rapid readout rate (6.2ms) allows increased dynamic range by avoiding saturation over bright pixels. Typically several reads are added for a single pixel (depending on altitude and speed) which increases SNR further. The snapshot detector readout eliminates smear artifacts. PRISM provides fully geolocated and georectified data, using integrated INS/GPS unit.

Data Products and Performance Characteristics: Table 5.2 summarizes the data products and accuracies of the relevant measurements provided by PRISM. PRISM performance exceeds the requirements given in the STM. PRISM significantly exceeds MODIS-equivalent SNR (i.e., 500-1000 SNR for 400-800 nm; Esaias et al. 1998) for improved detection and discrimination of dark water targets (Mouroulis et al 2012).

Figure 5.3 PRISM installed in the NASA ER-2 nose.

PRISM on the NASA ER-2 is proposed for this investigation. At 65 kft platform altitude, the spatial resolution of PRISM will be better than 20 m and the swath will be about 11 km. Due to the greater speed and endurance of the ER-2 compared to the King Air hosting DopplerScatt, PRISM will be able to image the same area as DopplerScatt while meeting a temporal coincidence requirement of less than 1 hour. Since it covers the entire area, it will overfly the MASS instrument multiple times every data collection period, providing cross-calibration of the higher spatial resolution data provided by MASS.

Platform Integration Characteristics: Since its first test flights in 2012 (Dierssen 2013), PRISM has successfully completed several deployments (Dierssen et al 2015, Hedley et al 2016; Fichot et al 2016, Thompson et al 2015; Stephens et al 2017) and was the main airborne instrument mapping coral reefs for the NASA EVS-2 CORal Reef Airborne Laboratory (CORAL) mission which completed its data collection phase in 2017. PRISM also participated in the HypSPIRI preparatory campaign aboard the ER-2 aircraft in 2018, mapping coral reefs off the Hawaiian islands. PRISM has been integrated on a variety of aircraft: Twin Otter (Glenn Research Center and Twin Otter International), Gulfstream-IV (G-IV), G-V, and the NASA ER-2 (Fig. 5.3).

5.3.3 MASS

Rationale: The MASS system is used to measure ocean waves, currents, sea surface height (SSH), and hyperspectral ocean color. Though installed on a slower aircraft, the flight profiles will be carefully designed to maximize the amount of collocated (space **and** time) measurements with DopplerScatt and the other in-situ platforms to ensure that STM requirements are met.

Instrument description: The Modular Aerial Sensing System (MASS) is an airborne instrument package developed at Scripps Institution of Oceanography (SIO; Melville et al. 2016) built around a high-resolution airborne topographic lidar collocated with video, infrared, and hyperspectral imaging systems. The system is coupled to a highly accurate GPS-aided inertial measurement unit (GPS/IMU), permitting airborne measurements of the sea surface displacement, temperature, and kinematics, with swath widths of up several kilometers, and horizontal spatial resolution down to 0.2 m. Over the last 7 years, the MASS has participated in 16 field campaigns, on topics ranging from air-sea interaction and physical oceanography studies, to coastal erosion, snowpack monitoring, and the built environment. Two MASS instruments are currently operated by the Air-Sea Interaction Laboratory (SIO), the first one funded by NSF.

Data Products and Performance Characteristics: Table 5.2 summarizes the data products and accuracies of the measurements provided by MASS.

Platform Integration Characteristics: Fig. 5.4 presents a schematic of the MASS accommodation on the Twin Otter DHC-6, operated by Twin Otter International (TOI, Grand Junction, CO, fleet of 26 DHC-6 aircraft) to be used in this experiment. The aircraft is equipped with two ports (forward and aft cabin) required for the MASS system. It also includes additional fuel capability (wing tip tanks + one internal auxiliary tank), a standard setup for NOAA offshore missions, that extends the Twin Otter range to about 8 useable flight-hours.

Figure 5.4 Proposed instrument installation on the Twin Otter DHC-6 aircraft showing the placement of the Modular Aerial Sensing System (MASS), and an A-size launch tube needed to deploy ALAMO profiling float or AXCTDs (not included in this proposal). The MASS includes a scanning waveform lidar, longwave infrared (LWIR) cameras, visible high-resolution camera, hyperspectral (VNIR) imager, and a GPS IMU system.

5.3.4 MOSES

Rationale: MOSES is capable of measuring ocean sea surface temperatures (SST) across a range of scales. The system will be accommodated on the NASA King Air together with DopplerScatt (Figure 5.2), providing SST measurements that are coincident with DopplerScatt measurements, meeting the STM requirements.

Instrument description: The Multiscale Observing System of the Ocean Surface (MOSES) is an aerial observing system that was developed jointly at UCLA and Ifremer (France). It is a relatively low cost package that includes off-the-shelf cameras, combined with accurate Applanix IMU/GPS to provide geo-referenced observations of the ocean surface. The primary camera in the system is a FLIR A6750SC SLS longwave infrared camera, providing SST at a resolution of several meters. The system accurately mosaics individual images to provide a near synoptic map of the mesoscale at $O(60^2 \text{ km})$. Atmospheric effects on the LWIR observations are mitigated by an algorithm that considers the pathlength of the observation for each individual pixel. This system was successfully used during two field campaigns in the Gulf of Mexico as part of CARTHE (D’Asaro et al., 2018).

5.4 Instrumentation Development Approach

All instruments are above TRL 6; no technology development is required. The DopplerScatt and PRISM instruments and platforms have been demonstrated in flight in the same configurations as are planned for this proposal. Data processing to generate L0–L2 products is either operational now (PRISM, AITT, FLIR) or will be made operational under existing NASA funding before the start of the proposed work (DopplerScatt, AITT funding). The MASS has been demonstrated in flight, successfully participating in 16 field campaigns over the last 7 years. The LWIR measurements are based on a widely used, commercially available instrument and have been proven during 2 recent campaigns. The in situ instruments and platforms described below have been used extensively by the co-Is and by many other investigators.

5.5 In situ measurement platforms and instruments

Instrumented Wave Gliders

The Liquid Robotics SV3 Wave Glider (Fig. 5.5) is the 3rd generation of the original wave glider. It is comprised of a surface buoyancy unit tethered to the subsurface propulsion unit which is equipped with an array of wings that can rotate about the “horizontal” axis. As the propulsion unit is raised and lowered in the water by the surface unit moving with the waves, and since the orbital motion of the waves decays exponentially with depth, the wings on the propulsion unit flap like swim fins moving the Wave Glider through the water. The Wave Glider carries a payload of instruments and a navigation and data acquisition computer and storage. The electronics are powered by batteries that are charged by solar panels.

Figure 5.5. Schematic of the Wave Glider platform (model SV3).

We will deploy a fleet of four wave gliders instrumented for detailed characterization of the lower atmospheric boundary layer and the upper 100 m of the water column (Table 5.3). The SIO team has used a similar configuration before (Lenain and Melville, 2014), and the WHOI group has conducted numerous 6-month Wave Glider deployments in the NASA SPURS-1 and SPURS-2 oceanographic field campaigns (Lindstrom et al, 2017).

Instrumentation	Measurement
Vaisala WXT530 Weather Station	2D winds, precipitation, atmospheric humidity, atmospheric temperature, air pressure.
NovaLynx Gill R3-50 Sonic Anemometer	3D winds, momentum & heat fluxes.
RBRmaestro3 C.T.D, Sea-Bird Electronics GPCTD	Conductivity, temperature, and depth
Turner Cyclops chlorophyll fluorometer	Chl-a fluorescence
RBRcoda ODOfast	Dissolved oxygen concentration
Wetlabs C-star	Beam transmittance
Xsens MTI IMU sensor	Glider position/attitude. Surface displacement, wave directional spectra.
Subsea Hemisphere V104 dual GPS receiver	Glider position. Surface displacement, wave directional spectra.
PME Thermistor Chain (40m length)	Temperature profile.
Teledyne Monitor 300kHz ADCP	Current profile.
Nortek Signature 1000 (with integrated IMU)	Current profile, Reynolds Stress.

Table 5.3. Primary instruments of the Wave Glider system and their application.

CARTHE-style biodegradable drifters

A low-cost, biodegradable drifter was developed for the Consortium for Advanced Research on Transport of Hydrocarbon in the Environment (CARTHE) Experiment (Novelli et al., 2017). The drifters accurately follow the currents of the upper 60 cm of the ocean, with wind-induced slip velocity below 0.5% of the 10-m neutral wind speed. These drifters are drawn into regions of strong submesoscale convergence, and one of our primary uses of these will be to identify and follow these convergence regions. When a sufficiently large number (~20) of them are deployed it is possible to make quantitative estimates of divergence and vorticity that can be compared to estimates from other platforms (e.g., D'Asaro et al., 2018).

Underway CTD

The Oceanscience Underway Profiling System (or Underway CTD system, or UCTD) measures seawater conductivity, temperature, and pressure. The UCTD system consists of a battery-powered, internally recording CTD with a tail spool, a tail-spool winder, and a winch. The system allows repeat casts approximately every 10 minutes, which allows 2-km resolution at a ship speed of 6 knots. The system has been used by many investigators in many oceanographic experiments; for example, during the NASA SPURS-1 experiment, the PI's team collected about 740 casts.

Seagliders

Seagliders are underwater autonomous submersible vehicles that utilize changes in buoyancy, pitch, and roll to move autonomously through the water and sample properties. A typical dive to ~1000 m can be completed in 4-6 hours and result in a horizontal distance traversed of about 3-5 km; thus, gliders travel a horizontal distance of ~20 km per day. Shallower dives (e.g., to 500m)

might be done to increase time and space resolution of the glider profiles, at the expenses of battery power. In addition to temperature and salinity sensors, the Seagliders will be equipped with velocity profilers sensors (Nortek ADCP; Todd et al. 2017), O₂ (Aanderra optode), microstructure (both temperature and shear sensors, from which we get a direct estimate of dissipation rates; Rainville et al., 2017), and optical backscatter (Sea-Bird ECO Puck) to estimate biologically relevant variables (backscatter, chlorophyll fluorescence, and absorption by colored dissolved organic matter).

Lagrangian Floats

The Lagrangian Float (LF) is a versatile platform for upper-ocean observations developed and built at APL/UW (D'Asaro 2003). These 1.5-m long instruments are designed to accurately follow the three-dimensional motion of water parcels, through a combination of actively-maintained neutral buoyancy and high drag provided by controllable flexible drogues. Accurate and highly adaptable automatic buoyancy control and relatively heavy payload distinguish LFs from other types of profiling floats. Operating in fully-Lagrangian water-following mode, the floats can track the three-dimensional pathways of subduction plumes associated with frontal convergence (Fig. 3.5, D'Asaro et al., 2018) and provide uniform sampling of the mixed layer turbulence (D'Asaro et al. 2014). They can also operate in isopycnal or isopycnal/Lagrangian modes in the pycnocline (D'Asaro 2008) allowing observations of vertical velocities associated with internal waves. For this experiment, the floats will be equipped with dual Sea-Bird SBE-41 conductivity/temperature sensors, dissolved oxygen sensors, and bio-optical fluorometer/scatterometer instrumentation (Sea-Bird ECO Puck). The floats will also carry Nortek Signature 1000 Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) for high-resolution measurement of vertical shear of horizontal and vertical velocities, as well as acoustic backscatter profiling (Shcherbina et al., 2018).

5.6 Modeling and Data Analysis Approach

5.6.1 Modeling approach

A key objective of this proposal is to develop observational tools that can be used to evaluate and improve model estimates of upper-ocean vertical property transports by submesoscale processes, leading to more realistic representation of these important fluxes in global ocean state estimates and climate models. We thus plan the following modeling components. First we will carry out an Observation System Simulation Experiment (OSSE) prior to the main campaign in order to test sampling strategies and fine-tune instrument deployment details. The OSSE will be similar in scope to that described in Wang et al. (2018) and will be based on the same submesoscale and internal wave admitting ocean simulation (2-km horizontal grid spacing, 90 vertical levels, including both atmospheric and tidal forcing), which was used in that study. Second we will use higher-resolution regional simulations (250-m horizontal grid and 270 vertical levels in the synoptic region and 30-m grid with non-hydrostatic dynamics in the fast sampling region) to predict, in a statistical sense, the vertical heat fluxes and "geophysical" noise that might be observed during the observational campaigns. Third, we will carry out simulations concurrent with the observational campaigns, with high-quality atmospheric and tidal forcing and lateral boundary conditions from large-scale data-assimilating models. Co-Is Molemaker and McWilliams will be responsible for modeling work based on the Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS) and co-I Menemenlis will be responsible for modeling work based on the MITgcm.

5.6.2 Data analysis approach

For Goal 1, the analysis will synthesize the various measurements shown in Figure 4.1 following the techniques used in D'Asaro et al. (2011), Thomas et al. (2015) and D'Asaro et al. (2018), e.g. Fig. 3.5. For each submesoscale feature, a coordinate system for analysis will be

defined, typically moving with the water or with observed features. The various data will then be cast into that coordinate system and mapped to form two- or three-dimensional time evolving descriptions of the temperature, salinity, density and velocity fields, their gradients including vorticity, divergence and strain, the mixing estimates, the optical properties and the surface and three-dimensional Lagrangian trajectories. This submesoscale synthesis will then be placed within a similar analysis of the mesoscale data including the Seaglider sections, the DopplerScatt surface velocity fields and constrained by operational altimetry and other data. This ensemble of submesoscale features and their mesoscale context will then be used for understanding how the model physics can be improved.

For Goal 2, a variety of analyses will address the various mechanisms controlling submesoscale air-sea interactions. First, the surface velocity and SST fields from the remote sensing and from the Goal 1 analyses will be compared to the DopplerScatt and in situ winds and air-sea fluxes to test the applicability of existing interaction mechanisms on the range of scales measured. These analyses will complement model studies attempting to evaluate these mesoscale theories on the submesoscale. Second, the vertical velocities measured by the Lagrangian float and by the Wave Glider array will be compared to vertical velocities predicted from the same theories. Finally, the fundamental physics associated with modulation of wind stress by submesoscale structures will be investigated by examining the changes in directional wave spectra and wave breaking rates across fronts, and comparing these to theoretical expectations and to the changes in the measured wind and DopplerScatt backscatter winds.

For Goal 3, the relationship between the cm-depth currents measured by DopplerScatt, the 0-60 cm depth currents measured by the surface drifters and the 1-60 m depth currents measured by the various ADCPs will be investigated both by finding all simultaneous co-located measurements and making direct comparisons and by investigating the scaling of each of these measurements with atmospheric forcing. Except in the regions of strongest submesoscale gradients, we anticipate that this will be a straightforward analysis.

For Goal 4, the challenge is to form a remote-sensing proxy for vertical transport and use this to evaluate the relative importance of submesoscale and mesoscale transports. As described in 3.1.4, the combination of surface divergence measured by DopplerScatt and SST or surface chlorophyll, as measured by aircraft imaging, will be used to form a proxy for the vertical heat flux or chlorophyll flux, that requires estimation of a vertical length scale h . Analyses will use in situ data from the Wave Glider array, guided by numerical simulation, to formulate a recipe to estimate h , and then test its accuracy using both models, the ensemble of remote sensing data and comparisons with mesoscale Omega equation estimates.

6.0 Science Management

6.1 Science Management Approach

The proposed organizational structure (Figure 6.1), led by a Program Management Office (PMO) at the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, is hierarchically organized around the principal components of the Program, Aircraft Measurements, In Situ Measurements, and Data Analysis and Modeling. The PMO includes the Program Principal Investigator (PI) (Tom Farrar) and a Science Investigation Manager (Paul Matthias). The PI has authority and responsibility for the successful delivery of the overall Program. The Science Investigation Manager, who reports to the PI, is responsible for Program reporting and deliverables. The PMO is complemented by a Field Deployment Management Team from NASA AMES ESPO. The FDM team will work with the PMO to manage the investigation, implement the field deployments and coordinate relevant aspects of programmatic reporting at investigation status reviews.

Each organizational component includes a Team led by a corresponding Subject Matter Expert who is a Program co-PI that reports to the PMO; the Aircraft Measurement Team is led by Ernesto Rodriguez of NASA/JPL, the In situ Measurement Team is led by Andrey Shcherbina of UW/APL, and the Data Analysis and Modeling Team is led by Eric D'Asaro, of UW/APL.

Figure 6.1. Program organizational structure.

The Aircraft Measurement Team Lead is supported by PRISM, DopplerScatt, MOSES, and MASS Instrument Leads, that

are responsible for integrating, testing, and operating the relevant instrument. The In situ Measurement Team Lead is supported by Ship Measurements, Wave Gliders, Lagrangian Floats, Drifters and Glider Groups, responsible for data collection from their respective allocated instrumentation. Finally, the Data Analysis and Modeling Team Lead is responsible for the related research and publications stemming from the data collected.

6.2 Science Risk Management

This investigation is low-risk as all of the instrumentation is mature (TRL 6 or higher). The remaining risks (summarized in Table 6.1) have been mitigated during the proposal formulation phase. Program Risks will be reviewed and refreshed quarterly by the PMO, FDM, and Team Leads, on or near the time of the quarterly Investigation Status Reviews (ISR).

Table 6.1 (next page). Program risks to science goals. Consequence (C*) levels are: (1) minimal; (2) small; (3) moderate mission risk or significant (implementation risk); (4) significant or “consumes all contingency” (implementation risk); (5) operations failure or overrun of budget (implementation risk). Likelihood (L*) levels are: (1) very low (<5%); (2) low (5-25%); (3) moderate (25-60%); (4) high (60-90%); (5) very high (>90%).

Risk Number	Risk	Pre-Mitigation		Mitigation Included in Baseline Plan	Post-Mitigation		Tracking and Point in Life Cycle when Risk will be retired
		C*	L*		C*	L*	
Airborne - 1	Poor weather (i.e., fog, clouds, rain, winds <3 m/s)	3	3	Weather predicts were used to sequence campaigns for California coast, and 200% campaign duration margin was applied when planning campaigns allowing for both schedule and cost mitigation.	3	1	During flight campaign
Airborne - 2	Airspace closures	3	2	Deployment area chosen such that there are no warning areas in the vicinity. Plan for early coordination with Air Traffic Control (ATC) ahead and during the campaign.	3	1	During flight campaign
Airborne - 3	Instrument anomaly/failure	4	1	Pre-campaign test flights and extensive ground testing. Instrument teams on the ground for troubleshooting and routine repairs; schedule flexibility.	4	1	During flight campaign
Airborne - 4	Instrument performance	5	2	Pre-campaign test flights and extensive ground testing. Planned for most likely component replacements by budgeting procurements 6 months ahead of campaign.	5	1	Ground and test flights pre-campaign
In Situ - 1	Glider or Wave Glider Instrument or Platform loss	4	1	Pre-campaign extensive laboratory testing. If loss occurs during a field campaign, reorganize remaining platforms, gliders and ship tracks to ensure adequate in situ data collection. Loss in Year 1-2 field campaign mitigation: replace the platform/instruments using project reserve.	4	1	During field campaign

6.3 Milestone Schedule

Proposed Program Milestones are provided below:

<p>Year 1: July 2019-June 2020</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> July 1, 2019: Project Start, begin Pilot Program Planning and Preparation. Deliver campaign airborne experiment plan and airborne CalVal report. Document Analysis of historical hydrographic data and various model output from the study site; comparison to previous glider vertical velocity and turbulence dissipation studies. January 15, 2020: Investigation Confirmation Review (ICR). January 2020: Complete integration and testing of MOSES airborne system and integration and testing of CTD + bio-optics package on Wavegliders. March 2020: Flight Readiness Review/Operational Readiness Review April 2020: Conduct 2-week Pilot Campaign (backup, Sept 2020). July 2020: Processing of Wave Glider data from pilot program complete.
<p>Year 2: July 2020-June 2021</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> November 2020: Publish Paper detailing 1st campaign DopplerScatt results. December 2020: Delivery of processed derived surface current and winds data products to NASA data center. February 2021: Complete first glider data manuscript. February 2021: Complete Second campaign airborne experiment plan and final airborne CalVal report. April 2021: Conduct 1-month Second Campaign.
<p>Year 3: July 2021-June 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> August 2021: Processing of glider data from the first field program complete. September 2021: Conduct 1-month Third Campaign. December 2021: Midterm Review April 2022: Paper detailing 2nd campaign DopplerScatt results complete. April 2022: Final Delivery of Second Campaign data to JPL PO.DAAC. May 2022: Paper on influence of environmental conditions (waves, winds, SST) on estimates of surface currents and winds complete. May 2022: Midterm Review.
<p>Year 4: July 2022-June 2023</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> September 2022: Science analysis, data delivery from Third Campaign to PO.DAAC data center, publications. December 2022: Final processing of glider data and production of the full vertical velocity / turbulent dissipation data set; comparison with ADCP-derived vertical velocities. June 2023: Development of relationship between surface velocities (DopplerScat) and turbulent dissipation (gliders), second manuscript complete. June 2023: Publish Updated derived product algorithms including wave and SST effects, and incorporating on situ guidance/observations/bias-corrections.
<p>Year 5: July 2023-June 2024</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document Final L2 reprocessed data for all surface current and wind derived products. Complete theoretical and numerical modeling effort, comparisons with field program observations, and publication of manuscripts. Analysis of field experiment data continues with the presentation of results at meetings and in peer-reviewed publications. <p>Project end date: June 30 2024.</p>

Note: Investigation Status Reviews (ISR) will be conducted at least quarterly.

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10.0 Operations Summary Table

Instrument		DopplerScatt		MOSES		PRISM		MASS	
Aircraft/Platform	Type	King Air B200		King Air B200		ER-2		Twin Otter DHC-6	
	Owner /Source	NASA Armstrong		NASA Armstrong		NASA Armstrong		Twin Otter International	
	Base of operations	Edwards AFB, CA		Edwards AFB, CA		Edwards AFB, CA		Marina, CA	
	Cost per hour (specify with or without fuel)	\$1,325 with fuel		\$1,325 with fuel		\$5,000 with fuel		\$1,225 with fuel	
	Platform stand up costs (if any)	N/A		N/A		N/A		\$1,900/day	
		Pilot	IOP	Pilot	IOP	Pilot	IOP	Pilot	IOP
	# of Flight hours	50	103	50	103	64	160	70	115
	# of Test flight hours	4	4	4	4	6	12	10	5
	# of Transit flight hours	3	3	3	3	3	3	10	10
Integration	Integration site	Edwards AFB, CA		Edwards AFB, CA		AFRC Palmdale, CA		TIO, Grand Junction, CO	
Deployment	# of deployments	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
	Locations (each site)	San Francisco, CA		San Francisco, CA		San Francisco, CA		San Francisco, CA	

NOTE: Transit hours are there and back from base of operations; IOP - Intensive Operations Period